

THE VAPOUR PRESSURE OF SOME STABLE AND UNSTABLE HYDRATES

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Vapour pressures of a number of stable and unstable hydrates have been determined by analytical method by absorbing the vapour in H_2SO_4 and determining the strength of the acid afterwards.

The author has been able to detect the presence of a large number of unstable hydrates by the differential thermo E. M. F. method (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 121). He has further observed that the life of these transient hydrates gets frozen when intimately mixed with some catalysers. The purpose of the present paper is to report on the vapour pressure of the stable and unstable hydrates, when the experiment is performed in a vibration-free environment.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrate, whose vapour pressure is required, is placed in one limb of an inverted U-tube and in the other limb concentrated sulphuric acid is kept. The tube is then evacuated and sealed. The whole arrangement is kept in a thermostat at a known temperature for 1 to 10 days. Water molecules from the hydrates distil off to the H_2SO_4 , till the vapour pressure of the mixture of H_2O and H_2SO_4 equals that of the hydrate; when further distillation stops. By titration of the H_2SO_4 solution after the experiment is over, its strength is determined and hence its equilibrium vapour pressure.

The characteristic hydrates were prepared by keeping the samples at the temperatures at which they are formed for one day and then they were carefully removed to the experimental tube in such a way that they did not absorb moisture in the process. In the case of $CuSO_4$ the temperature of the thermostat was 35° and in the case of $BeSO_4$, 14° . In some cases, the above arrangement was connected to a capillary oil manometer and the vapour pressure read directly. Here also H_2SO_4 acted as an absorbent of the evolved water molecules.

The fact that the hydrates have the characteristic composition as published in the previous paper at a particular temperature after they have remained in the thermostat for a long time was also checked by the determination of the percentage of the cationic radical in the final sample of the hydrate.

RESULTS

The data obtained are given in Table I, where x represents the number of molecules of H_2O in the hydrate and p is the vapour pressure in mm. of Hg.

Evidently from the figure the hydrates reported are genuine as shown by the vapour pressure measurement. The equilibrium value of the vapour pressure comes with extreme slowness and sometimes the samples are to be kept in the thermostat for 8 to 10 days before measurements can be relied on. This point is also borne out by the work of Patrick and McGowan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 946).

TABLE I

	Stable hydrates.		Unstable hydrates.			Stable hydrates.		Unstable hydrates.	
	α	β	α	β		α	β	α	β
CuSO ₄ mixed with silica powder at 35°	1	0'21	4½	15'42	BeSO ₄ mixed with silica powder at 14°	1	0'11	1½	0'31
	2	3'42	4½	16'11		2	0'62	4½	5'11
	3	11'22	—	—		3	1'21	—	—
	4	14'13	—	—		4	3'84	—	—
	5	17'41	—	—		5	6'23	—	—
CuSO ₄ in presence of gold dust at 35°	1	0'28	4½	15'51	BeSO ₄ mixed with sodium silicate	1	0'08	½	0'03
	2	3'49	—	—		2	0'54	—	—
	3	12'00	4½	16'23		3	1'19	1½	0'29
	4	14'02	—	—		4	3'52	—	—
	5	16'83	—	—		5	6'11	4½	4'82

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